

Recycling system for biocomposite decking

Biocomposite is a collective term referring to fibre-reinforced materials with partly natural origin. Fibre content ranges from 15% to 75%. Decking materials for outdoor applications is the biggest market segment for biocomposites produced from local sawmill side streams. The thermoplastic end product is recyclable and several Wood Plastic Composite (WPC) producers promote “a take back system for wood-plastic composites”. Innovative producers invent their own system for collection. Consumers return products to the dealer with recycling take-back boxes or order boxes at home. Taken back products reprocessed and made reusable as decking boards again.

Regional coverage and transferability

Reverse logistic practices are feasible and economically viable for many recyclable products as described here for decking boards. The transferability is depending on the market demand and the occurring volumes in regions.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ High percentages of postconsumer material can be used and upcycled as e.g. decking material for a second life
- ▶ Waste management with a take-back system drives market acceptance of these recycled products and adds value for environmentally friendly products
- ▶ Innovative solutions and functional use of side streams such as for outdoor decking improves biomass profitability
- ▶ Decking products can have a lifetime guarantee of 10 to 25 years, which is rather durable for outdoor products and therefore presents an advantage compared to common practices of solid wood decking
- ▶ Developing new recycling systems inherits advantages for the whole value chain